

FIFDM – ADVANCED 3D PRINTING WITH CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCEMENTJ. Schlimbach¹, M. Domm²¹ Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe, Manufacturing Science, Erwin-Schrödinger-Straße 58, 67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany, jens.schlimbach@ivw.uni-kl.de, www.ivw.uni-kl.de² Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe, Technology Transfer, Erwin-Schrödinger-Straße 58, 67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany, matthias.domm@ivw.uni-kl.de, www.ivw.uni-kl.de**Keywords:** additive manufacturing, CFRP, continuous fibers, FDM, process development**ABSTRACT**

FRPC are an ideal lightweight construction material as they combine low density with very high mechanical performance. However, there is generally a lack of automated processes for the production of geometrically complex components with load-specific and thus economical fiber reinforcement. In contrast, AM processes allow the fully automated manufacturing of individualized and almost arbitrary complex components without the need for special tools. However, a major disadvantage of 3D-printing processes, especially for polymer materials available today, is the limited stiffness and strength. The introduced concept of the so-called Fiber Integrated Fused Deposition Modelling (FIFDM) is based on the Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) or Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF), a well-known extrusion 3D-printing process for thermoplastic polymers. In contrast to other 3D-printing methods such as sinter, binder, or light curing, extrusion processes have the advantage that continuous thermoplastic strands are being processed which opens the possibility to integrate continuous and oriented fibers. In order to demonstrate the use of continuously fiber reinforced thermoplastic strands, a standard 3D-printer was rebuilt which allows the layup of continuously fiber reinforced polymer strands in all spatial directions. As one of the central process steps, the extrusion process was analyzed in terms of nozzle temperature, conveying, and cooling speed. While the length of the extruded strands was the target value for process stability, fiber distribution, void content, roundness, and widening of the extruded strands were investigated as target values for extrusion quality. New evaluation methods for determining roundness and fiber distribution of continuously fiber reinforced strands were developed for quantification purposes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composites (FRPC) are an ideal lightweight construction material for the automotive, aerospace, medical, and sports industries as they combine low density with very high mechanical performance. The length and direction of the fibers in the component are most relevant for the reinforcement effect. The largest possible reinforcing effect of the fibers is achieved if they are continuously aligned in the direction of load. However, there is generally a lack of automated processes for the production of geometrically complex components with load-specific and thus economical fiber reinforcement. In contrast, Additive Manufacturing (AM) processes allow the fully automated manufacturing of individualized and almost arbitrary complex components without the need for special tools. As a result, the interest in AM processes is increasing in virtually all industry sectors, especially in the fields of rapid prototyping, direct tooling, and direct manufacturing. In 2016, the global 3D-printing market recorded sales of €5.62 billion with an average growth rate of 28% over the last 4 years [1]. However, a major disadvantage of 3D-printing processes, especially for polymer materials available today, is the limited stiffness and strength.

This led to the idea of combining FRPC with AM to overcome the respective disadvantages and thus, enable a flexible and automated manufacturing process for complex structures with high specific mechanical properties.

1.1 STATE OF THE ART

There exist several process variants to reinforce 3D printed polymer parts with fillers and short fibers [2-7]. Parallel to the development of the FIFDM process initial efforts have been made according to continuous fiber reinforcement into the FDM/FFF process [8-24]. A few companies already sell FFF/FDM based 3D-printers with continuous fiber reinforcement, examples can be found in [16,21]. The concepts on how the fibers are integrated into the process differ a lot. Mostly, the fibers are dry and need to be impregnated during the process or within the nozzle. Geometrically, most of the approaches do only allow the layup of the fibers in-plane therefore restrictions regarding load-optimized fiber orientation are inevitable.

For the optimization of the extrusion in the FIFDM process, insights from related processes such as extrusion and pultrusion can be taken into consideration. Especially here, the expansion of the strand at the nozzle outlet is considered one of the most evident effect. When pre-impregnated semi-finished products are used two causes are relevant for this effect: Firstly, the abrupt drop of pressure and stress state at the nozzle outlet. The shear force induced between nozzle wall and strand affects the orientation and thus the elastic deformation of the polymer melt. The pressure drop at the nozzle outlet causes a relaxation of elastic elongation which consequently provokes a strand expansion. For this effect the nozzle geometry is considered to be the main influencing factor [25-27]. Secondly, residual stresses in the semi-finished product which are released during reheating can cause the strand expansion. As reasons for residual stresses i.e. stored energy due to alignment of the viscoelastic polymer, its crystallization, applied fiber compaction, thermal expansion, and pressurization of air filled bubbles are itemized [28,29].

1.2 FIFDM PROCESS

The concept of the so-called Fiber Integrated Fused Deposition Modelling (FIFDM) is based on the Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) or also called Fiber Filament Fabrication (FFF), a well-known extrusion 3D-printing process for thermoplastic polymers. Within this process, a thermoplastic polymer strand is squeezed through a nozzle where it is heated-up above melting temperature before it is placed on a printing bed layer by layer [30]. In contrast to other 3D-printing methods like sinter, binder, or light curing, extrusion processes have the advantage that continuous thermoplastic strands are being processed. This opens the possibility to integrate continuous and oriented fibers. The FIFDM concept has the following outstanding characteristics [31,32]:

- *The processing of continuous fibers:* The process uses almost completely impregnated and continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic strands. Compared to separate supply of fiber and polymer or not impregnated semi-finished products like commingled yarns, no impregnation step is required during printing. This leads to higher material output, process speeds, and fiber volume content.
- *The possibility to align the reinforcement fibers not only in-plane, but in all directions of space.* This is achieved by fast cooling of the fiber reinforced polymer strand (FRPS) after leaving the print nozzle to prevent the structure from collapsing when placed into free space.

Figure 1 shows the schematic of the standard FDM/FFF in comparison to the novel FIFDM process. In further studies, the FDM/FFF technology has been fundamentally modified to accomplish the use of continuous fiber reinforced strands. A new extrusion unit and a cooling system were developed for this purpose. Furthermore, a cutting unit has been designed which is required for discontinuous placing. With this setup the feasibility of the FIFDM process could be shown by printing a first demonstrator [31]. The biggest challenge within the process, especially when printing into free space, is temperature control of the strand material. Subsequently, a thermal finite element model was developed to simulate the temperature profile of the strand material for process design. A preheating unit can be used to reduce the temperature gradient in the print nozzle, thus increasing the process speed or material output. The process can be divided into a preheating, conveying, extrusion, and placing step. As first mechanical characterization of FIFDM printed samples has shown the potentials and challenges of the process [32].

Figure 1: Scheme of FDM/FFF (left side) and FIFDM process (right side)[32]

All relevant process parameters were identified to characterize the FIFDM process. As one of the central process steps, the extrusion process was analyzed in terms of nozzle temperature, conveying, and cooling speed. While the length of the extruded strands was the target value for process stability, fiber distribution, void content, roundness, and widening of the extruded strands were investigated as target values for extrusion quality. New evaluation methods for determining roundness and fiber distribution of continuously fiber reinforced strands were developed for quantification purposes. The results are directly incorporated into further development of the technology.

1.3 OBJECTIVES

Based on the development of the FIFDM process, the goal is to identify those process variables that have the highest influence on the print result and define process boundaries.

2 EXPERIMENTATION

2.1 Setup and Materials

The printer used was a German RepRap X400CE 3D-printer modified according to the schematic diagram in Figure 1, right-hand side. The print head has two feed and extrusion units and is moved on two rails in the X/Y-direction. The Z-movement is achieved by the height adjustment of the print bed. The printing area is 400 mm x 400 mm x 380 mm with a specified reproduction accuracy of ± 0.01 mm. The control software used was Simplify3D (version 2.2.2). The core of the new extrusion unit for the continuous fiber reinforced polymer strand is a nozzle with a slightly conical inside bore and a cylindrical exit zone from 1.9mm diameter. To improve the accuracy of the material feed, a driven and structured roller is used within the conveyor unit. A second, non-driven roller presses the polymer strand against the driven roller to minimize slippage. For more precise temperature control, a compressed air cooling system consisting of four cooling nozzles was additionally installed. Up to 6 bar pressure can be adjusted via a throttle valve.

The material used was a continuous, glass-fiber reinforced polypropylene strand (GF-PP), which is an intermediate in the production of LFT pellets (Figure 2, right-hand side). The diameter is $1.89 \text{ mm} \pm 0.4 \text{ mm}$. 30 vol .-% and the pore content at $6.04 \pm 1.4 \text{ vol .-%}$.

Figure 2: Experimental setup (left side) and semi-finished product used (right side) [32]

2.2 Experimental Setup

In order to obtain an overview of the influence of process parameters on extrusion quality a screening test plan was defined. For the extrusion process the 3 control parameters process speed, extrusion temperature, and cooling rate were identified as most relevant. For the experiments, the process speed was set between 100 mm/min and 1000 mm/min. Based on preliminary tests [32] and a thermal simulation, the values for the extrusion temperature between 210 °C and 290 °C were specified. The cooling rate can be set between 0 m/s and 66 m/s. The test plan is summarized in Table 1.

Due to the small number of control parameters, a full-factor experimental design was chosen, with a repetition of 3 for each process parameter combination. The full-factor experimental design also allows identifying interactions between the process parameters. The tests were carried out randomly to minimize the risk of systematic errors.

Table 1: Test plan – control parameters and setting

Process Speed [mm/min]	Extrusion Temperature [°C]	Cooling Rate [m/s]
100	210	0
1000	290	66

The length of the extruded strands was 140 mm. These were extruded directly from the print nozzle into the free space perpendicular to the printing bed. For microscopic characterization, 15 mm samples were taken from the center of each extruded strand. The microsections were analyzed by *Leitz Aristomet* microscope and the software *analySIS docu*.

2.3 Analysis methodology

For the quantification of the influence of process parameters on extrusion quality, possible target criteria were identified that relate either to the external shape or to the quality of the composite. Regarding the external shape, roundness, expansion, length, and curvature are considered and regarding the composite quality the void content and fiber distribution, respectively. The following methods were used:

- A measuring tape for extrusion length and straightness. The actual and vertical lengths of the extruded material are measured and given as the percentage of the predefined conveying length.
- Microscopic images of micrographs for roundness, strand expansion, void content, and fiber distribution. Roundness was measured according to [33], where the microscopic picture is analyzed regarding the area of bulges and the average bulge height and

measured against optimum. For the strand expansion the actual cross-sectional area of the extruded strand is measured against the nozzle outlet. Void content is calculated by grey value analysis. Fiber distribution is also defined and quantified according to [34], see Figure 3. There is a radial value where the cross section is divided in 8 rings of equal area and fiber content is measured against ideal homogeneous fiber content. The second criterion for fiber distribution is cartesian, where the distance between the centroid of the fiber area and the centroid of the total cross section is calculated. Total value for fiber distribution is defined as mean value of both criteria.

Figure 3: Schematic for the determination of roundness (left side) and radial fibre distribution (right side) [34]

3. RESULTS

The results of the parameter study for each target criterion are displayed in Fig. 5-7:

- Extrusion length and straightness depending on extrusion temperature (T), process speed (v), and cooling rate (C) (Fig. 5)
- Roundness and expansion of the extruded strands (Fig. 6)
- Void content and the fiber distribution (Fig 7)

Figure 4: Extrusion parameter study: Evaluation of extrusion length and straightness [34]

Figure 5: Extrusion parameter study: Evaluation of roundness and strand expansion [34]

Figure 6: Extrusion parameter study: Evaluation of void content and fiber distribution [34]

The values for the extrusion length are well below 100% for all trials caused by increased friction in the nozzle which then causes slippage in the conveying unit. This effect is due to the use of fiber reinforced material. Straightness values are noticeable low for $T = 290\text{ °C}$, $v = 100\text{ mm/min}$, and $C = 0\text{ m/s}$.

Regarding roundness, except for settings with high extrusion temperature and no active cooling, the values can be improved compared to the start values of the semi-finished product. Values for expansion are between -4.52% and 40.96% .

The values for void content (1.62% to 22.93%) show that a reimpregnation of the semi-finished product (average void content: 6.04%) during the extrusion process is possible with appropriate parameter selection. The values for fiber distribution show acceptable results for the right parameter set (up to 87.74%).

The quantification of the influence of each parameter (extrusion temperature, process speed, and cooling rate) on the target criteria follows the statistical method of comparing mean values according to [35]. The effect (difference between two mean values) on the respective target value is calculated and compared with typical confidence intervals (95% , 99% and 99.9%), which indicate the significance of the respective effect. For comparison, the numerical values were normalized to the value of the 99.9% . Larger numerical values correspond with higher effects. The colour scheme shows the significance value of the effect, the direction of the arrows

indicates to the direction in which the parameter must change to improve the respective target value.

Effects of Control Parameters on Target Criteria			
Target Criteria	T	v	K
Extrusion Length	200 ↑	1 -	13 -
Straightness	187 ↓	147	211 ↑
Roundness	227 ↓	67 -	273 ↑
Expansion	148 ↓	14 -	193 ↑
Void Content	97 ↓	7 -	99 ↑
Fibre Distribution	75 ↓	12	152 ↑

Numeric value: Effect value related to 99.9% confidence interval

↑
↓ Direction of the parameter with which the criterion can be improved

Significance of effects depending on confidence intervals:

- Most Significant
- Significant
- Indifferent
- No Indication

Figure 7: Effects of control parameters on target criteria [34]

Figure 7 shows that the cooling rate and the extrusion temperature have a significant influence. A lower nozzle temperature and faster cooling have a positive effect on the target criteria roundness, strand expansion, void content, and fiber distribution. This underpins the statement already cited in the introduction that the strand expansion is the dominant effect in the extrusion of continuously fiber reinforced polymer strands. This is due to the higher energy absorption in the nozzle due to high die temperature and low process speed, resulting in lower polymer viscosity, which in turn reduces the resistance of the material against strand expansion. With the parameter setting $T = 290\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $v = 100\text{ mm/min}$, and $C = 0\text{ m/s}$, the worst results are achieved. Strand expansion is also the dominant effect that with longer dwell time and higher temperature in the nozzle a further impregnation of the semi-finished strand can be improved [36]. Cooling directly at the nozzle outlet can freeze the strand shape below melting temperature before it has time to expand. Interestingly, the temperature plays a minor role within the chosen boundaries; extrusion speed on the other hand has a high influence. Slower speed means not only higher energy absorption in the nozzle but also more time within the cooling area. In combination is slower speed therefore good for reimpregnation and lower strand expansion.

The extrusion length mainly depends on the nozzle temperature: the higher the temperature, the longer the extrusion length. The effect is based on lower friction in the nozzle due to reduced viscosity of the polymer [37], which reduced the slippage of conveying unit, too. In regards to the criterion straightness, it can be observed that all three control parameters are impacting. The effects calculated here are, however, strongly dominated by one parameter setting ($T = 290\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $v = 100\text{ mm/min}$, $C = 0\text{ m/s}$) and therefore, must not be overestimated (see Figure 6).

4 CONCLUSIONS

The FIFDM process is an innovative process concept for the 3D-printing of endless fiber reinforced thermoplastics. In addition to the in-plane printing, FIFDM enables fiber orientation according to the load in all spatial directions (out-of-plane) without a special tool. Starting from the FDM or FFF, the process for the use of fiber reinforced strands has been modified with regard to nozzle design, transport unit, temperature control and cutting unit as well as a cooling unit were added. In the presented study, the influence of the process parameters nozzle temperature, conveying speed and cooling rate on the extrusion process resp. on the print result. The target criteria were extrusion length, straightness, roundness, expansion, void content and fiber distribution of the extruded strands.

Of all investigated parameters, the effect of the cross-sectional widening (expansion) while leaving the nozzle is the most influencing on the quality of the extruded material. This effect is dependent on the nozzle geometry, the increase in energy consumption of the fiber-reinforced polymer strand in the pressure nozzle, and the cooling rate after leaving the nozzle. Active cooling can minimize or prevent expansion. In addition, it could be shown that a further impregnation of the semi-finished product strand

is possible in the extrusion process. Increased friction in the nozzle, which depends on the polymer viscosity, causes increased slip in the printing unit. This effect is higher at lower nozzle temperatures. Based on the investigations presented here, the influence on the deformation and placement of the extruded strands is investigated in another experimental parameter study.

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